

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Hydrolysis of Tri-4-(2-phenylisopropyl)phenyl Phosphate Ester in Acid Medium

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The effect of substituents on the hydrolysis of arylphosphate esters having C–O–P linkage^{1,2} have been studied exhaustively by Mhala *et al.*^{1,3,4} and it has been established that the effect of substituents of graded polarity⁵ not only affects the reaction rates but also alters the course of reaction path. The aim of the present study is to see whether or not (+I) positive inductive effect of two methyl groups at carbon atom that directly attached to phenyl phosphate and benzene ring in the rear stereoposition in tri-4-(2-phenylisopropyl)phenyl phosphate ester inducing +M and +E effects (due to benzene ring) would bring about acid catalysis.

Results and Discussion

Effect of ionic strength : Whether maximum at 4.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl is due to (i) ionic strength effect or (ii) water activity or both, may be decided by carrying out kinetic runs using appropriate mixture of HCl and KCl at constant ionic strength. A plot of rate constant vs acid molarity gave three straight-lines meeting at a point on the rate axis. This shows that the contribution of neutral species (K_{No}) towards overall hydrolysis is constant while slopes of these lines are specific acid-catalysed rates (K_H^+). Further, the linear plot of $\log K_H^+ C_H^+$ vs ionic strength (μ) meets at rate axis making a slope $b'_{H^+} = -0.072$ and intercept $\log K_{Ho}^+ = 79.43 \times 10^{-5} \text{ min}^{-1}$, the specific acid-catalysed rates at zero ionic strength. Employing these terms in second empirical term of Dubye-Hückel equation and modifying it logarithmically the rates are calculated for conjugate acid species.

The effects of acid, ionic strength and solvent are presented in Table 1.

$$\log K_H^+ C_H^+ = \log K_{Ho}^+ + \log C_H^+ - b'_{H^+} \mu \quad (1)$$

$$K_{\infty} = 32.00 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ min}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

On the basis of equations (1) and (2) the contribution of neutral and conjugate acid species gave computed rates, $K_o = K_H^+ C_H^+ + K_{\infty}$. The negative value of the slope b'_{H^+} indicates that salt-effect is negative.

From the results of Table 2 it is clear that calculated rates resemble fairly well with observed rates upto 4.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl. However, the rates beyond 4.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl deviates from normal values which is attributed to decrease in reactivity of neutral species as well as conjugate acid

Effect	Concn.	Observation	Inference
Acid	0.1–4.0 M HCl	A plot of $\log K_o$ vs pH gave unit slope and increasing to a maximum	Probability of first order reaction
	4.0 M HCl	Maximum	May be due to (i) ionic strength effect, (ii) water activity. It could be decided by study of ionic strength effect
<i>Table 1(Contd.)</i>			
Ionic strength	1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 μ KCl and HCl mixture	Plot of acid molarity vs rate constants gave three lines meeting at rate axis (K_{No}) with slopes (K_H^+). Plot of $\log$ rate constants (K_H^+) vs ionic strength (μ) with intercept $K_{Ho}^+ = 79.43 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ min}^{-1}$ slope $b'_{H^+} = -0.072$	Rates calculated by using K_H^+ , b'_{H^+} terms in employing Debye-Hückel eqn. estimated rates have been summarised in Table 2
Solvent effect	30% Dioxane 60% Dioxane	$173.78 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ min}^{-1}$ $181.50 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ min}^{-1}$	Incorporation of water molecule, and insignificant rise in rates is due to better proton donating property of dioxane in acid medium
Substrate concn.	2.5, 5.0 and 7.5 $10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	Rate constants remain unaffected	First order

species by (i) negative effect of ionic strength or (ii) decrease due to water activity. Thus the rates have been computed by applying Bronsted-Bjerrum equation,

$$K_H^+ C_H^+ = K_H^+ C_H^+ \exp b'_{H^+} \mu (a_{H_2O})^n$$

where $(a_{H_2O})^n$ represents water activity term. The value of $n = 5$ and $\bar{b} = 6$ respectively are calculated for 5.0 and 6.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl.

Various correlation plots (figures not shown) like Hammett plot⁶ (0.285), Zucker-Hammett plot (0.553), Bunnett plot ($w = 10.00$, $w^* = 5.45$) and Bunnett-Olson plot⁷ ($\phi = -1.69$) postulates bimolecular rates of hydrolysis, indicating high dependence of the rates on water activity

ity⁸. The Arrhenius parameters calculated for 3.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl are $\Delta E = 21.50$ kcal mol⁻¹, $\lambda = 14.60 \times 10^7$ s⁻¹ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -23.59$ e.u. and for 5.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl are $\Delta E = 23.29$ kcal mol⁻¹ = 21.17×10^8 s⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -18.28$ e.u. The conjugate acid species has been shown to hydrolyse bimolecularly by various correlation plots. The above Arrhenius parameters also support bimolecular hydrolysis while isokinetic relationship (Table 3) indicates P-O bond fission.

TABLE 2—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF TRI-4-(2-PHENYLISOPROPYL)PHENYL PHOSPHATE AT 97±0.5°

HCl mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ K _c (Calcd.) min ⁻¹	10 ⁵ K _c (Obsd.) min ⁻¹
0.5	68.64	67.60
1.0	99.29	99.12
2.0	145.76	144.89
2.5	163.82	158.48
3.0	176.87	173.78
4.0	195.68	204.17
5.0	116.91	112.20
6.0	47.52	48.97

TABLE 3—COMPARATIVE ISOKINETIC RATE DATA FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF SOME TRIPHOSPHATE ESTERS VIA THEIR CONJUGATE ACID SPECIES

Phenyl phosphate	Temp. °C	10 ⁵ K _c s ⁻¹	ΔE kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	Bond fission	Ref.
Phenyl	100	—	20.8	27.96	P-O	2
2,6-Dimethyl-	98	0.12	21.59	19.19	P-O	10
2,4-Dinitrophenyl-	25	0.79	18.8	-26	P-O	12
4-Chloro-3,5-dimethylphenyl-	98	2.38	27.36	15.42	P-O	14
4-Chloro-3-methylaniline-	97	0.84	27.55	-7.41	P-N	15
4-(2-Phenylisopropyl)-	97	2.89	21.5	23.5	P-O	This work

Solvent effect has been studied for conjugate acid species. The insignificant increase in rates may be attributed to the better proton donating property of dioxane in acid medium. Higher the polarity of the solvent, higher will be the rates⁹. Hence, the formation of transition state in which charges are dispersed, undoubtedly formed¹⁰, indicates bimolecular mechanism of the hydrolysis of the tri-ester. Thus the mechanism for the hydrolysis of tri-4-(2-phenylisopropyl)phenyl phosphate is shown in Schemes 1 and 2.

Experimental

The triester was synthesised by the reported method¹¹. A mixture of parent phenol in benzene and POCl₃ was stirred at 80° for 25 h and then distilled at reduced pressure. The first fraction distilled at 118° was rejected and the second fraction of pungent smelling liquid was supposed to be dichloridate of monoester, distilled at 133–

50°. The residue left in R.B. flask was digested in hot 0.1 N NaOH solution, washed several times, filtered and crystallised from absolute ethanol to yield the product, m.p. 155° (Found : P, 4.38. Calcd. : P, 4.56%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 110 (C-H aliphatic) and 3 000–2 900 cm⁻¹ (C=C-C=C).

References

- M. M. MHALA, M. D. PATWARDHAN and G. KASTURE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 149.
- P. W. C. BARNARD, C. A. BUNTON, D. KILLERMAN, M. M. MHALA, B. SILVER, C. A. VERNAN and V. A. WELCH, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1966, 227.
- M. M. MHALA and A. V. KELLEDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 476.
- M. M. MHALA and M. D. PATWARDHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 704.
- R. JAMES, COX, JR. and O. B. RAMSAY, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, 64, 317.

- 6 J F BUNNETT and F P OLSEN *Can J Chem* 1967 **44** 7899
- 7 J F BUNNETT *J Am Chem Soc* 1961 **83** 4956
- 8 C A BUNTON and V J SHINER *J Am Chem Soc* 1961 3214
- 9 C K INGOLD *Structure and Mechanism of Inorganic Chemistry* Cornell University Press Ithaca 1953 Chap VIII
- 10 F H WESTHEIMER *Chem Rev* 1961 **61** 268
- 11 P RUDERT *Chem Ber* 1893 **26** 565
- 12 C A BUNTON and S J FARBER *J Org Chem* 1969 **4** 7677
- 13 M M MHALA and R S KUSHWAHA *Indian J Chem Sect A* 1989 **28** 420
- 14 R S KUSHWAHA and B K TIWARI *Acta Chimica Indica* 1986 **4** 207
- 15 R S KUSHWAHA B K TIWARI P SINGH S UPADHYAYA and I S SHARMA *J Inst Chem India* 1988 57